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Provision of a Terminology Service for Semantic Ontology Mapping – First Toolset Prototype

Content

Executive Summary.....	2
1 Introduction	3
2 Previous Work.....	4
2.1 Samplly MDR.....	4
2.2 German Biobank Node.....	4
2.3 MOLGENIS.....	6
3 Data Harmonisation as a Major Step in the Preparation Process for the BBMRI Network Readiness	7
4 General Architecture Design.....	9
5 Demonstrator.....	12
6 MDR2MOLGENIS.....	15
7 Open Challenges and Outlook	19
References	21

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Executive Summary

BBMRI-ERIC is a pan-European consortium with the goal to establish and operate a research infrastructure to facilitate the access to the sample collections of participating biobanks. The ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC, as part of this initiative, aims to support the implementation of BBMRI-ERIC by providing the necessary IT services.

This document is part of a series of reports regarding the deployment of a toolset for the mapping of the distinct biobanking terminologies. This deliverable (BBMRI-ERIC CS IT D8.3 / ADOPT 3.5) describes the functionalities and the development of a first toolset prototype, which is based on reusing existing tools (e.g. the Molgenis BiobankConnect tool (Pang et al. 2015a, 2016) and the Sampil Metadata Repository (Kadioglu et al. 2016, Lablans et al. 2015, Storf et al. 2017) and integrating those into a data harmonisation pipeline with new developments such as a "MDR to Molgenis Converter" (MDR2MOLGENIS). The document further describes the currently proposed workflow for integrating a biobank (and its respective local data sources/data elements) through the MDR and Molgenis functionalities into the future BBMRI ERIC network.

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1 Introduction

In coordination with the BBMRI-ERIC CS IT project the ADOPT project is organised in eight work packages. WP1 is responsible for the coordination of the project. This involves not only the overall management of ADOPT but also the monitoring of the project's performance. For this reason several indicators will be developed by WP2 (Data Sets), WP4 (Access) and WP7 (Rare Diseases). While WP2 will provide the first BBMRI-ERIC- wide disease cohort consisting of mapped data on colon cancer, WP7 will develop the concept for a Common Service for Rare Diseases in order to collate projects and initiatives that address this subject. WP3 and WP4 will lay the basis for these efforts. The development of an IT-Gateway (WP3) enables a close interaction between European biobanks that facilitates the trans-national cross-biobank search for suitable biospecimens and omics data (WP6). In addition, WP4 will improve the users' access to the biobank connection by granting simplified access to documents, published results and samples. Moreover, a Stakeholder Forum (WP5) will be established to encourage exchange of experience and knowledge between patients, users, investigators, and industry and to offer a platform for discussions. Eventually WP8 (Internationalisation) is in charge of expanding BBMRI-ERIC within and also beyond the European Union as well as strengthening relationships with organisations related to its activities.

Since the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC proposal is consistently aligned with the BBMRI-ERIC Common Service IT, the CS IT will take over of the tasks of ADOPT WP3. This includes the provision of a biobank registry (Task 1), the development of IT tools regarding security architectures (Task 2) and ontology mapping (Task 3), the provision of interface Connectors (Task 4) and the application of the colon cancer use-case (Task 5).

This deliverable covers one of the specific objectives of Task 3, namely the development and deployment of a toolbox to support the mapping of data attributes/value lists, biobank meta data as well as clinical case/sample description attributes to a central core terminology.

The necessity of such a mapping toolset is due to the non-comparability of data from different sources. Every partnering institution usually refers to a particular data scheme adjusted for its own use. This proceeding might create data collections that are insufficiently described and consequently unsuitable for secondary use, e.g. future research performed by external researchers. In order to avoid this pitfall and to ensure the interoperability between data sources, a toolbox will be developed. This toolbox will provide the software components that will support the mapping of the biobanks' existing data on an agreed upon common terminology for the purpose of data harmonisation.

In the following, the report outlines the specifications and functionalities that are considered essential for the mapping/harmonisation process. Moreover, the development of the first prototype of this toolset will be described.

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2 Previous Work

2.1 Samply MDR

Samply is an open source software (for the largest part) that consists of multiple components (https://bitbucket.org/medinfo_mainz/). Its core components are:

- Samply.MDR: Metadata Management. The MDR follows the ISO 11179 standard (<http://metadata-standards.org/11179/>) and enables the definition of data elements and their associated value sets. Furthermore, data elements can be arranged in hierarchies and annotated with a rich set of attributes, such as data type or regular expression for value validation. The Samply.MDR can also be extended by making use of "slots", which allow the definition of additional arbitrary attributes. Another main feature of the MDR is its user interface. The integrated web interface allows for easy registration of new data elements, including an automatic validation of a data element's structure.
- Samply.EDC.Osse: "The OSSE registry framework is a toolbox that supports the setup of disease-related registries in the area of rare diseases. The framework consists of several local components that each registry compound runs by itself and central components that are operated for several (ideally all) OSSE-type registries." (https://bitbucket.org/medinfo_mainz/samply.edc.osse/wiki/Home)
- Samply.Auth (not open source): Central authentication within the Samply system.

For the integration into the ADOPT data harmonization processes the Samply MDR is the most relevant component (Kadioglu et al. 2016).

2.2 German Biobank Node

Within BBMRI-ERIC, it has been discussed from the very beginning to base the first prototype on the open-source software Samply (Lablans et al. 2015), a system developed for the *German Cancer Consortium* (DKTK). Samply's core functionality is to interconnect biobanks and to allow for running feasibility queries, which were created within the *Samply.Share Broker's GUI*, across the whole network. The participating biobanks are running a "bridgehead" (*Samply.Share Client*), which accepts incoming queries from the *Samply.Share Broker* (Lablans et al. 2015). For metadata management, a metadata repository, the Samply.MDR (Kadioglu et al. 2016), has been developed. Since the DKTK biobanks are based on the commercial Software CentraXX (Kairos GmbH), a CentraXX DWH Adapter has been developed. This component then issues queries to the CentraXX system.

Within the German Biobank Node (GBN) prototype, the Samply system has been successfully integrated into a hybrid querying architecture, which also comprises *Informatics for Integrating Biology and the Bedside* (i2b2) for issuing and running queries (Mate et al 2017a). As shown in

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Figure 1 (upper right corner), the bridgehead (*Samply.Share Client*) has been extended by a *Query Translator* and an *i2b2 DWH Adapter* (based on "li2b2" from <https://github.com/li2b2>) to allow for issuing queries on the i2b2 system. Since data structures and data schemas in the "Samply world" and the "i2b2 world" are different, a schema-/query translator (OmnyQery) has developed which performs an on-the-fly query translation (Mate, Vormstein et al. 2017b); in other words, the GBN network is capable of integrating biobanks with diverse data sets and different data warehouse architectures (CentraXX and i2b2). In addition, it is also possible to inject queries into the whole architecture by making use of the i2b2 webclient (upper left corner in Figure 1). This successful pilot implementation illustrates the flexibility, but also complexity, of such hybrid networks and can be a starting point for further ADOPT/BBMRI-ERIC CS IT discussions and design decisions.

Figure 1. One of the two architectures from the German Biobank Node (GBN) prototype (modified excerpt from (Mate and Vormstein 2017a)).

The currently proposed ADOPT prototype is based on a slightly different design decision. Instead of applying a "on-the-fly" query translation, we aim at defining one core data terminology and performing the data harmonisation already beforehand as part of the ETL processes. In other words, the biobanks will have to perform the data harmonisation/integration locally, and the Connectors will store only already harmonised data. For the latter harmonisation process the analysis of already existing, and openly available tools has shown the potential of the MOLGENIS BiobankConnect lexical and semantic matching modules to provide an easy user interface to significantly speed up the biobank harmonisation process and also other forms of biomedical data Integration (Pang et al 2014).

2.3 MOLGENIS

The MOLGENIS was originally developed as a toolkit for bioinformaticians with a simple language to model biological data structures and user interfaces. At the push of a button, MOLGENIS' generator suite automatically translates these models into feature-rich, ready-to-use web applications including database, user interfaces, exchange formats, and scriptable interfaces (Swertz et al. 2010). Since then, this toolkit has continuously expanded and especially the MOLGENIS/connect (BiobankConnect) module may be efficiently integrated into the ADOPT harmonisation Pipeline. MOLGENIS/connect provides a semi-automatic system to find, match and pool data from different sources using ontology-based query expansion to overcome variations in terminology (Pang et al. 2016).

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3 Data Harmonisation as a Major Step in the Preparation Process for the BBMRI Network Readiness

Data harmonisation is a complicated process that needs to be supported by software tools. What follows is an exemplary work flow of the harmonisation process from a biobank's point of view. It includes various steps that are ideally supported well by the selection of IT tools. However, some of the tools mentioned here are just initial proposals for which usefulness and feasibility still have to be assessed:

1. Select the variables that correspond to those variables required for the Sample Locator.
2. Collect all the necessary metadata for the required variables as it corresponds to the biobank's own data, tabulate it in the data model format required by a metadata repository (MDR).
3. Translate the data into English.
4. Upload the variable metadata into the MDR and make sure the upload went correctly using data upload report tools and by manually checking the data (→ user friendly MDR import tool, including informative report and error logs).
5. Map the local variables with the required variables stored in the MDR (→ mapping tool).
6. One variable at a time, and using the mapping tool: compare the units/options for the MDR required data set, and decide whether the variable is compatible as such or are conversion rules needed before the variable can be used. Write the conversion rule (or use suitable formula from the formula bank). Save the updated local variable metadata into your local space in the MDR. (→ tool to support transformation of variables).
7. Map the local ontologies used in the biobank's data to the supported ontologies of BBMRI-ERIC, using an ontology mapping tool (→ ontology mapping tool, includes also support for translation).
8. For local ontologies that are already mapped to the supported BBMRI-ERIC ontology, that mapping could be readily used and the links between the ontologies saved in the MDR (→ MDR ontology support tool).
9. During the individual-level data upload process, there ideally should be an automatic conversion process that converts the local ontologies to the supported ontology (→ ETL tools).
10. Set up a data warehouse software (= Connector) provided by BBMRI-ERIC CSIT onto the biobank's own server, and verify that there is proper connection between the local data warehouse, the central Sample Locator software and the central MDR.
11. Prepare the individual (or sample)-level data files for the biobank's sample collection/s.
12. Upload the individual-level data to the data warehouse/Connector using the available import tools (→ Connector import tools should at best do the transformations of the data based on the transformation rules automatically, during the import process and provide import log and error log to the user to verify the data has been properly imported,

the transformations of the data properly done as specified in the MDR, and the ontology mapping correctly done).

13. Test the Sample Locator to see that the data is now available for sample availability queries.

There are already some existing data harmonisation tools, ontology mapping services, metadata repositories, and translation tools available, but there is nothing between them that would unite them. This is where 'WP8 data harmonisation toolset' would come in, working as a glue combining different softwares to operate together using the same simple data model.

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4 General Architecture Design

The Sample Metadata Repository (Sample MDR; <https://mdr-test.ccp-it.dtkk.dkfz.de>; compare Kadioglu et al. 2016, Lablans et al. 2015, Storf et al. 2017) will act as the central storage for all relevant data descriptions in context of the biobank environment. The core data elements that provide the basis for all network queries are defined in the Core_Query namespace (BBMRI-ERIC Core Terminology Demonstrator (CTD)). These network queries are performed and stored by the Sample Locator. The Sample Locator is a central service, just as the MDR, and is linked to the local environment of the biobanks. Each biobank's local environment consists of a proprietary local Biobank Information Management System (BIMS) as well as a generic Connector installation. The Connector functions as the link between the external CS IT services and the local biobank. It comprises three components: (1) the MOLGENIS mapping tool (Pang et al. 2015a, Pang et al. 2016), (2) the MOLGENIS data storage and (3) the tool that fetches the queries from the Sample Locator.

(1) MOLGENIS BiobankConnect mapping tool: MOLGENIS supports the semi-automatic mapping of data elements. For this purpose it requires two input files: one file defining the original data input and second file describing the target schema on which the original data elements should be mapped. The original data input file consists of two Excel sheets: one for the data attribute metadata description and the second with the original sample/donor data. Thus, in order to obtain harmonised data, each biobank needs to create such a MOLGENIS Excel input file with its local data. It has to include both a data sheet and an attributes sheet for all entities. The attributes sheet is generated from each biobank's dedicated MDR namespace (Biobank X Namespace). Therefore the first step in a harmonisation process is, that a biobank has to create its own MDR namespace and define its own data elements and corresponding metadata in this namespace. Then this Excel input file needs to be uploaded into the MOLGENIS database. The MOLGENIS target schema input file is based on the definition of the ADOPT biobank network core data elements (still to be defined within ADOPT). All such core data elements also need to be defined in the MDR Namespace (currently BBMRI-ERIC Core Terminology Demonstrator (CTD)). Thus, the Core_Query schema is created from the MDR Core_Query Namespace and deposited in the MOLGENIS database. Subsequently, the MOLGENIS Core_Query schema can be used to map the data from the MOLGENIS biobank data sheet into the MOLGENIS database "data mapped".

(2) MOLGENIS data storage: For our purpose, we also aim to use MOLGENIS as data warehouse in order to store the mapped data by the MOLGENIS BiobankConnect mapping tool. In a broader sense, MOLGENIS can be regarded a data warehouse (DWH), as it fulfills the basic requirements of basic data integration and retrieval. It can be used to load data via the EMX format and supports mapping expressions, which allow for data transformations. The data schema can be designed in different ways, and for BBMRI-ERIC we are currently

working together with WP2 to design a schema that fulfills the requirements of the BBMRI-ERIC Connector. On the retrieval side, MOLGENIS features basic functions to filter the database content from the user interface. A thorough functionality for data analysis (such as OLAP in fully-featured DWH environments) is not part of MOLGENIS; however, this is not required for BBMRI-ERIC, as the Connector will perform all data retrieval. MOLGENIS features a REST interface, which allows for querying its content. For further data analysis, the MOLGENIS database can be accessed directly, bypassing the REST interface. Future versions of the BBMRI-ERIC platform may extend MOLGENIS with another, further featured DWH or database. It has been in the discussion to use OSSE or i2b2 in future version the BBMRI-ERIC infrastructure.

(3) Tool to fetch and execute queries, as described in the ADOPT deliverable 3.6 "Biobank Connector specification and reference Connector implementation": The ultimate goal of the BBMRI-ERIC Connector is to execute queries that have been created in a central location on the Connector's DWH. By reusing the above-mentioned REST interface, incoming queries from this central location will be executed on the DWH. Similar to the GBN project, we aim to implement a translator logic that translates Sample query syntax into a syntax that conforms to MOLGENIS' query formalism. This translator will be implemented by WP2 (in close collaboration with WP8) and may build upon previous work from the GBN project (Mate et al. 2017b).

By providing those three components, it is possible to perform queries in all participating biobanks even though they describe their data elements in different ways. The Connector will only store already harmonised data. The user builds his query with the Sample Locator based on the data elements taken from the Core_Query namespace. The Connector fetches this query from the backend of the Sample Locator/Broker (component (3)) and queries each biobank's local database "data mapped" (component (1)). Since this database consists of the local biobank data mapped to the Core Terminology, the Connector receives feedback if the required data elements are available in a specific biobank and can then report it back to the Sample Locator. The General Architecture Design is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The General Architecture Design of the toolset.

5 Demonstrator

In order to verify the actual operability of the general architecture design, we prepared a demonstrator. Since in this first step no real biobanks and real world biobank data were involved, for testing purposes dummy datasets for a "Fake Biobank" and a "Imaginary Biobank" were created (Connector DWH mapper test.xlsx). Further, since the final definition of a core data terminology for the ADOPT / BBMRI ERIC CS IT still has to be defined within other work-packages, a demonstrator dummy core data terminology has been created (MI-ABIS_Sample_SampleDonor.xlsx) and defined within MDR. The procedure was as followed:

(1) Three namespaces were defined in the Demonstrator MDR (<https://mdr-test.ccp-it.dtkk.dkfz.de/>):

(I) Namespace "BBMRI-ERIC CTD" includes several elements from MIABIS_Sample_SampleDonor.xlsx. This file consists of selected items from MI-ABIS 2.0, and thus will be the basis for our demonstrator by providing the core terminology.

(II) Namespace "Imaginary Biobank" includes all items from "Fake biobank data for Connector DWH mapper test.xlsx / sheet Imaginary biobank data descript". This will be the namespace of the demo biobank "Imaginary Biobank".

(III) Namespace "Fake Biobank" includes all items from "Fake biobank data for Connector DWH mapper test.xlsx / sheet Fake biobank data descript". This will be the the namespace of the second demo biobank "Fake Biobank".

(2) A parser - MDR2MOLGENIS - with a RESTful interface to the MDR was developed. The input parameter for the parser is the name of a MDR namespace. MDR2MOLGENIS reads all the data elements and their descriptions and subsequently creates a new Excel-file with an attributes sheet in accordance to the respective syntax of the MOLGENIS input files. For demonstration purpose, we run it three times with "BBMRI-ERIC CTD", "Imaginary Biobank", and "Fake Biobank" as input and create three different EMX input files. It will result in obtaining the files "CTD-Molgenis_Target Schema.emx", "Imaginary Biobank.emx", and "Fake Biobank.emx" (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The operating principle of MDR2MOLGENIS.

(3) The data sheet or sheets of the files "Imaginary Biobank.emx" and "Fake Biobank.emx" can subsequently be loaded with the demo "patient data" from "Fake biobank data for Connector DWH mapper test.xlsx / sheet Imaginary biobank raw data" and "Fake biobank data for Connector DWH mapper test.xlsx / sheet Fake biobank raw data" respectively.

(4) After generating those three EMX files, MOLGENIS is able to map the file "CTD-Molgenis_Target Schema.emx" with the files "Imaginary Biobank.emx" and "Fake Biobank.emx" in order to generate the database "data mapped" in the local environment of the respective biobank (Figure 4).

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Figure 4. The mapping process of MOLGENIS in the biobank's local environment.

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6 MDR2MOLGENIS

MDR2MOLGENIS is a parser, which creates the so called EMX files for using in MOLGENIS out of an MDR namespace. The RESTful interface to the MDR enables this process. Using this tool without installing anything is possible due to the integration of a Jetty server (<https://eclipse.org/jetty/>). Figure 5 shows the work flow of this parser.

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Figure 5. The MDR2MOLGENIS parser algorithm.

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The name of the desired namespace is required to be specified by the user. After receiving the input, the program retrieves the namespace members by a function as outlined below. As it can be seen, the programme differentiates the namespace into subgroups and data elements (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Hierarchical structure of an exemplary namespace.

The data elements are saved in a list of all data elements. The subgroups one by one repeat starting of getting their appropriate members, same here: data elements are saved in the list and the subgroups repeat starting. The previous illustration might clarify how the programme operates. The numbers of the different data elements and subgroups demonstrate the sequence in which the programme realises the hierarchical structure. For this reason, the numbers of the left side are the minor ones of the hierarchical tree. This shows that the programme will finish the left big “tree” first. The second one on the right hand will be processed after that.

Once that has been done, one data element after another from the list is picked out and stored in the EMX file. This file is an Excel file which consists of two different sheets. The first one is for the attributes; every column stands for another attribute and every row stands for another data

element. The second sheet is a value set, where one can express permitted values. A small selection of the BBMRI-ERIC core schema and its related value set can be seen in Figure 7. The correctly written attributes, elements and permitted datatypes are necessary for the following steps of integrating data.

Attributes sheet

name	entity	dataType	description	refEntity	idAttribute	nullable
Material_Type	BBMRI-ERIC_CTD	String	The biospecimen type saved from a biological entity for te			
Protocol_available	BBMRI-ERIC_CTD	Bool	The protocol/s that was/were used to process the sample			
Sample_creation_date	BBMRI-ERIC_CTD	date	The date the sample was created in the form currently de			
Sample_ID	BBMRI-ERIC_CTD	String	Unique ID of the sample within a sample collection, often			

Related valueset

Material_Type	Protocol_available	Sample_creation_date	Sample ID
Blood	WAHR	1992-08-04	7896
DNA	FALSCH	1992-08-04	7897
Faeces	WAHR	1992-08-04	7898
Immortalized Cell Lines	FALSCH	1992-08-04	7899
Isolated Pathogen	WAHR	1992-08-04	7900
Other	FALSCH	1992-08-04	7901
Plasma	WAHR	1992-08-04	7902
RNA	FALSCH	1992-08-04	7903
Saliva	WAHR	1992-08-04	7904
Serum	FALSCH	1992-08-04	7905
Tissue (Frozen)	WAHR	1992-08-04	7906
Tissue (FFPE)	FALSCH	1992-08-04	7907
Urine	WAHR	1992-08-04	7908

Figure 7. Small section of an attribute sheet and a related value set of the BBMRI-ERIC CTD namespace.

Once all steps are completed and there are no further un-processed data elements or sub-groups in it, the file can be downloaded. Early experiences with MDR2MOLGENIS indicate that it is a very useful tool for in integrating data sets with MOLGENIS.

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7 Open Challenges and Outlook

Our work on MOLGENIS is still in progress. Until now, details of MOLGENIS' internals still need further evaluation. Mapping the already described biobank data sets to the core schema of the BBMR-ERIC CTD schema, however, has been successful. There are different types of problems, which could not be solved until now. For example the "Imaginary Biobank" has its "Sample Type" described as a Boolean. Therefore, it contains different data elements as can be seen in Figure 8. The core schema only describes its "Material Type", which is obviously the same, in an enumerated list of values. Figure 8 shows that the "Imaginary Biobank" has a similar data set in different datatypes. At this point, it remains to be analysed how to match those values.

Figure 8. Challenge of mapping different datatypes.

The integration of MOLGENIS into our harmonisation pipeline will be further tested and evaluated with other data sets. The creation of such testing material that is more similar to the core schema is important for understanding how MOLGENIS creates the different mapping expressions, what the critical parameters for a self-sufficient mapping are and how MOLGENIS classifies its own mapping expression. Also, it has to be further evaluated how MOLGENIS utilises its matching algorithms. In the testing phase some matches were automatically created, but some were only suggested. It is also possible to reuse already created matching expression due to another element where MOLGENIS did not suggest any. For the future it is essential to figure out, how to implement further mapping expressions in MOLGENIS.

Also MOLGENIS itself provides many different modules for mapping data sets. These tools have to be reviewed and it needs to be clarified in which cases they are useful (e.g. the "Mapping Service", "SORTA", "Tag Wizard" and "Ontology Manager"). It is important to clarify in which way these tools can be helpful for a better use of MOLGENIS.

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As already mentioned, mapping with MOLGENIS is not as easy as it seems to be. Until now many questions arose while working with mapping expressions. There are many different mapping expressions needed in the harmonisation process. A person without any IT background may not be able to deal with these. This is the reason why it should be discussed if it is possible to develop something like a dictionary or a repository for these mapping expressions and the corresponding meaning. This offers the possibility that every biobanker can upload data on his own. This may lead to personnel savings and it would make the process of mapping data sets more comfortable.

Also it has to be discussed, if a semi-automated translation service should be included in MDR2MOLGENIS. The translation services might be very helpful as the step before mapping the data. This step can facilitate the mapping process. Therefore, some data elements can be brought into the right schema without using MOLGENIS. It must be considered which languages might be good in supporting the mapping process.

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